

A STUDY OF TRENDS IN B2C ONLINE BUYING IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

In today's busy world online buying plays an important role in shopping. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find out the B2C online buying trends in Coimbatore district. A sample of 100 respondents' was conveniently selected from Coimbatore District. The selected samples are analyzed using simple percentage, chi-square test and correlation analysis test. It is found that four variables namely age, educational qualification, occupation and monthly income are found to be significant association with consumer satisfaction towards online buying. The study also concluded that educational qualification, occupation, monthly income have significant association with consumers preference towards B2C online buying.

Key Words: Online, Buying, Satisfaction, Consumers, E-Commerce & Problem

Introduction:

Business to Consumer (B2C) is business or transactions conducted directly between a company and consumers who are the end-users of its products or services. The business-to-consumer as a business model differs significantly from the business-to-business model, which refers to commerce between two or more businesses. While most companies that sell directly to consumers can be referred to as B2C companies, the term became immensely popular during the dotcom boom of the late 1990s, when it was used mainly to refer to online retailers, as well as other companies that sold products and services to consumers through the internet.

Trend of Online Buying:

Online buying or E-commerce was first introduced in the 1960s via an electronic data interchange (EDI) on value-added networks (VANs). The medium grew with the increased availability of internet access and the advent of popular online sellers in the 1990s and early 2000s. Amazon began operating as a book-shipping business in Jeff Bezos' garage in 1995. EBay, which enables consumers to sell to each other online, introduced online auctions in 1995 and exploded with the 1997 Beanie Babies frenzy.

As mobile devices became more popular, mobile commerce has become its own market. With the rise of such sites as Facebook and Twitter, social media has become an important driver of e-commerce. The changing market represents a vast opportunity for businesses to improve their relevance and expand their market in the online world.

Types of E-Commerce:

- ✓ **Business-to-Business (B2B):** Business-to-Business (B2B) e-commerce encompasses all electronic transactions of goods or services conducted between companies.
- ✓ **Business-to-Consumer (B2C):** The Business-to-Consumer type of e-commerce is distinguished by the establishment of electronic business relationships between businesses and final consumers.
- ✓ **Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C):** Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C) type e-commerce encompasses all electronic transactions of goods or services conducted between consumers.
- ✓ **Consumer-to-Business (C2B):** In C2B there is a complete reversal of the traditional sense of exchanging goods.
- ✓ **Business-to-Administration (B2A):** B2A e-commerce encompasses all transactions conducted online between companies and public administration.
- ✓ **Consumer-to-Administration (C2A):** The Consumer-to-Administration model encompasses all electronic transactions conducted between individuals and public administration.

Online Buying Websites in India:

Flipkart.com	Univercell.in
Infibeam.com	Smartshoppers.in
Ebay.in	Lynx-india.com
Shopping.indiatimes.com	Mediahome.in
Shopping.rediff.com	Themobilestore.in
Futurebazaar.com	Timtara.com
Homeshop18.com	Ezoneonline.in
Yebhi.com	Gadgets.in
Amazon.com	Snapdeal.com
ShopClues.Com	Jabong.Com
Caratlane.Com	Naaptol.Com

Review of Literature:

Jean Éthier, Pierre Hadaya and Jean Cadieux (2006) explored the impact of the quality of a web site on the cognitive process leading to consumers’ emotions considered as direct antecedents to shopping behaviors and operationalized as mental states of readiness arising from the appraisal of events. A parsimonious theoretical model was defined and tested with data collected from 215 web-shopping episodes during which consumers were shopping for low-touch products. Analysis of the results showed that web site quality had a positive impact on the cognitive appraisal of situational state, which in turn influenced five of the six emotions of the proposed model: liking, joy, pride, dislike, and frustration.

Satyabhusan Dash & K. B. Saji (2008) revealed the role of consumer self-efficacy and website social presence in customer's adoption of B2C online shopping mediated by trust, perceived usefulness, and perceived risk. The most significant outcome of the study is that the consumer self-efficacy and website social-presence affect trust, perceived usefulness and perceived risk in the online customers, and in turn positively influence the customer's intention to purchase products online.

Prof. Ashish Bhatt (2014) observed that online shopping is gaining popularity among people specially the younger generation but in today scenario to become equally popular among all age groups e-marketing will have to cover a longer distance. The main objective of this study is to find Consumer Attitude towards Online Shopping in Selected Regions of Gujarat. People from different age groups are doing online shopping regularly. The research paper resulted that attitude of consumers is changing with the time. In a country like India, consumers are finding online shopping very comfortable because of many variables like cash on delivery, customization or personalization of the websites, home delivery etc.

Upasana Kanchan, Naveen Kumar and Abhishek Gupta (2015) revealed that online purchase behaviour of customers in India. The paper stated that online shopping is gaining popularity among people of young generation. Higher income groups and educated people are purchasing more via e-retailing websites and people have hesitations in doing online shopping due to security concerns. Today people are resistant to change because of technological complexity in making online purchase. The research concluded that companies involved in online retailing should focus on building trustworthy relationship between producers and customers.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the demographic profile of the B2C online buying consumers in Coimbatore District.
- ✓ To find the consumers satisfaction towards B2C online buying consumers.
- ✓ To identify the consumers preference towards B2C online buying consumers in Coimbatore District.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Coimbatore District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Coimbatore District is the study area. A total of 100 B2C B2C online buying consumers are taken as sample. These respondents were conveniently selected in Coimbatore District. Primary data is collected through well structured questionnaire. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Chi-Square Test
- ✓ Correlation Analysis

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents: Table no.1 describes the demographic profile of the B2C online buying consumers which is taken for the study. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (68%) of the respondents are male, (39%) whose age group is under 26 to 45 years, most (53%) of the respondents are graduates, maximum number (31%) of respondents are professionals, the monthly income of (46%) respondents is Rs.10,000 to Rs.25,000, (65%) belongs to nuclear family, number of members in respondents family are between 2 to 5, (43%) respondents purchase are influenced through advertisement, (35%) of the respondents purchase electronic items through online, (52%) of the respondents pay cash on delivery for their B2C online buying and (35%) of the respondents purchase monthly through online buying.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	68	68
Female	32	32
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	36	36

26 to 45	39	39
Above 45	25	25
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	14	14
Graduate	53	53
PG	33	33
Occupation		
Professional	31	31
Employee	29	29
Business	26	26
Others	14	14
Monthly Income		
Up to Rs.10000	22	22
Rs.10000 to Rs.25000	46	46
Above Rs.25000	32	32
Type of Family		
Joint	35	35
Nuclear	65	65
Number of Members		
Upto2	24	24
2 to 5	56	56
Above 5	20	20
Influence to Purchase		
Family	27	27
Advertisement	43	43
Friends/Relatives	30	30
Products purchased through online		
Clothes/ Accessories	26	26
Tickets	25	25
Electronic Items	35	35
Books/Medicines	14	14
Frequency of Purchase		
Daily	12	12
Weekly	28	28
Fortnightly	25	25
Monthly	35	35
Mode of Payment		
Debit cards/Credit cards	48	48
Cash on Delivery	52	52

Table 2: Relationship between the Demographic Profile and Level of Satisfaction towards B2C Online Buying

Variables	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
Gender	4.789	5.991	NS
Age	11.654	9.488	S
Occupation	13.987	12.592	S
Educational Qualification	11.967	9.488	S
Monthly income	13.390	9.488	S
Number of Members	6.324	9.488	NS
Type of Family	3.852	5.991	NS

Relationship between Demographic Variables and Consumers Level of Satisfaction towards B2C Online Buying:

Table no.3 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables of the consumers and their level of satisfaction towards B2C online buying. It is clear that , the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there does not exists any significant association between gender, number of members in family and type of family of the B2C online buying consumers. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists a significant association between age, occupation, educational qualification and monthly income of the B2C online buying consumers. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3: Online Buying Consumers Preference Associated with Demographic Variables Correlation Analysis

Factors	R	r2
Gender	0.045	0
Age	0.032	0
Educational Qualification	0.078*	0.05
Occupation	0.016*	0.02
Monthly Income	0.99*	0.06
Type of Family	0.059	0.002

* Significant at five percent level

- ✓ **Educational Qualification:** Correlation analysis indicates that these two variables are positively correlated indicating that B2C online buying preference is more with respondents who are graduates. The coefficient of determination (r^2) shows that occupation accounts for 5 per cent of the variation in the level of preference at five percent level of significance.
- ✓ **Occupation:** Correlation analysis indicates that these two variables are positively correlated indicating that B2C online buying preference is more with respondents who are professionals. The coefficient of determination (r^2) shows that occupation accounts for 2 per cent of the variation in the level of preference at five percent level of significance.
- ✓ **Monthly Income:** The correlation analysis shows that these two variables are positively correlated indicating that as the monthly income increases the level of preference of the respondents also increases. The coefficient of determination (r^2) shows that monthly income of the respondents account for 6 percent of variations in the level of preference at five percent level of significance.

Conclusion:

B2C online buying in India is growing between 2012 and 2016. Internet penetration is increasing in India due to the increasing base of social networking sites and sale of mobiles India. B2C online buying is one of the most attractive, widely accepted, highly appreciated business in present world. Preference of people towards B2C online buying have changed tremendously. Although the consumers are satisfied with B2C online buying they also face some problems due to many technological and false advertisement. Once consumers problems are taken into consideration with a sharper focus on online business that in turn benefit both companies and consumers.

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